

OPTIMIZATION OF THE HYDROCARBON PRODUCTION PROCESS FROM NATURAL GAS

JABBAROVA LALA YUSIF

Institute of Physics, Ministry of Science and Education Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku

CABRAYILOVA ILHANA ELNAR

master Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract. *At present, the principal method for producing synthetic motor fuels from natural gas is the Gas-to-Liquids (GTL) technology. In its hydrocarbon-based form, the modern GTL process is a two- or three-stage technology that relies on catalytic reactions. In the first stage, the relatively inert paraffinic hydrocarbons that constitute the major portion of natural and associated petroleum gases are converted into a more reactive mixture of carbon monoxide and hydrogen, commonly referred to as synthesis gas (syngas). This conversion is primarily achieved through steam reforming or autothermal reforming, while partial oxidation is employed less frequently.*

These technologies are well established and are widely employed in industry for the production of ammonia, methanol, oxo alcohols, and other chemical products. The first stage of the GTL process is the most capital-intensive; therefore, any improvements in this area can significantly enhance the overall economic efficiency of the process. The second stage, namely the synthesis of hydrocarbons from carbon monoxide and hydrogen (the Fischer–Tropsch synthesis), represents the core stage of the GTL process, as it determines both the yield and composition of the resulting hydrocarbons, as well as the necessity and method of subsequent product upgrading and refining. The economics of this stage largely depend on the ability of the catalyst to promote the reaction while minimizing the formation of gaseous hydrocarbons, which constitute the principal by-products of the process. In the third stage, the hydrocarbon products are upgraded to commercial-quality fuels through hydrocracking or hydroisomerization. At this stage, excessive gas formation also adversely affects process economics and overall efficiency. It should be noted that the development and operation of natural gas fields are generally less technologically complex than those of oil fields. However, the costs associated with the transportation and storage of natural gas are significantly higher than those for liquid hydrocarbons. The development of natural gas processing technologies worldwide is directly influenced by the distance between the gas field and the end consumer, and consequently by transportation costs. Natural gas is transported either in compressed form through pipelines or in liquefied form using specialized tankers. Another viable approach is the chemical conversion of natural gas at the production site into liquid hydrocarbons, followed by transportation of these petroleum products using conventional methods, such as rail or marine transport. In a number of cases, this latter approach proves to be the most economically efficient method for transporting natural gas. Environmental concerns have stimulated considerable interest among petroleum companies in the processing of carbon-containing gases. Unfortunately, current oil production practices in our country generally do not provide for the efficient utilization of associated petroleum gas. In the most favorable cases, associated gas is recovered as relatively inexpensive but difficult-to-transport liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) or reinjected into the reservoir to enhance oil recovery. However, it is often simply flared. Consequently, the development of modern methods for the utilization of associated petroleum gas has become a particularly important challenge in the creation of environmentally safe and waste-free oil production technologies. One approach to addressing this problem is the liquefaction of associated petroleum gas and the transportation of the liquefied gas to major consumers, such as gas and energy suppliers in Japan [1].

This strategy is most effective in regions with substantial reserves of onshore natural gas. Another method for the utilization of associated gas involves the production of synthetic crude oil

using Gas-to-Liquids (GTL) technology, followed by its transportation and processing together with conventional crude oil. It should be noted that interest in the Fischer–Tropsch synthesis and other alternative methods for the production of hydrocarbon products is largely influenced by conditions in global oil markets [2].

Thus, during the 1960s, the rapid development of the petroleum refining and petrochemical industries led to a significant decline in research activities related to the Fischer–Tropsch synthesis. At present, political instability in a number of OPEC member countries, including Venezuela, Iraq, and Nigeria, has contributed to sharp increases in global oil prices and has stimulated renewed interest in the development of technologies for the production of synthetic petroleum products. At the same time, the development of gas chemistry (the chemical conversion of natural gas), as well as the implementation of gas-to-chemicals processes aimed at producing valuable carbon-containing compounds, is constrained by several factors. Natural gas production sites are often located far from industrial centers, and its transportation requires substantial capital investment and energy consumption. Advanced chemical processing of natural gas near production sites is also difficult to implement, as it demands significant investment, highly qualified personnel, and appropriate infrastructure. In general, the practical realization of gas-to-chemicals technologies is associated with high capital costs [3].

To date, there are only three industrial plants worldwide producing synthetic fuels via Gas-to-Liquids (GTL) technology: the Shell plant in Malaysia with a capacity of 1.2 million tonnes per year, the Moss gas plant in South Africa with a capacity of 1.1 million tonnes per year, and the Oryx plant operated by Qatar Petroleum and Sasol in Qatar with a capacity of 1.5 million tonnes per year. At present, there is a growing trend toward the practical implementation of GTL processes. Pilot and semi-industrial facilities for the production of synthetic hydrocarbons using this method are also operating in South Africa, the United States, Norway, Italy, and the United Kingdom. Almost all leading global oil companies (Shell, BP Amoco, ExxonMobil, Conoco, and others) are involved, to varying degrees, in the development of their own GTL projects. The interest of oil companies in this process is driven by the need to expand the feedstock base, as well as by the opportunity for corporate growth through investments in new projects for the production of middle distillates from low-cost natural gas in remote fields located in countries such as Malaysia, Qatar, Nigeria, and others. It was projected that by 2010, the total capacity of GTL plants would exceed 20 million tonnes per year [4,5].

The primary modern method for producing synthesis gas and hydrogen is the oxidative conversion of methane. Three main approaches to this process are known:

- (a) Steam reforming: $\text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO} + 3\text{H}_2$, $\Delta H = +226 \text{ kJ/mol}$;
- (b) Dry (CO₂) reforming: $\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2 \rightleftharpoons 2\text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2$, $\Delta H = +264 \text{ kJ/mol}$;
- (c) Partial oxidation: $\text{CH}_4 + 1/2\text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2$, $\Delta H = 44 \text{ kJ/mol}$.

Combinations of these reactions are also used, for example steam–CO₂ reforming of methane. For industrial implementation, the strongly endothermic reactions (a) and (b) require an external heat supply. In contrast, reaction (c) is exothermic. The integration of endothermic methane reforming processes with exothermic partial oxidation enables the production of synthesis gas with little or no external heat input (autothermal reforming, ATR). Current improvements in natural gas conversion processes are mainly focused on reducing capital investment and increasing the scale of individual process units. The following technologies are considered the most promising in this regard:

1. **Next-generation ATR** (autothermal reforming): reduction of the steam-to-carbon ratio from the current value of 0.6 to 0.2–0.3 without causing degradation of the reactor metal.
2. **Heat-exchange reforming**: a combined process in which the heat generated during ATR is utilized to drive the steam reforming reaction.
3. **Membrane-assisted reforming**: a process based on the use of dense ceramic membranes that enable ionic oxygen transport from air into the reaction zone.

The main stage of the GTL process is the synthesis of hydrocarbons from synthesis gas. This stage determines both the quality and quantity of the target products. The catalyst and process configuration of this stage form the core of the entire GTL technology and represent the primary subject of licensing. The Fischer–Tropsch synthesis can be considered as an oligomerization of carbon monoxide, which may be expressed in simplified form as:

This is an exothermic reaction occurring in the presence of catalysts. The Fischer–Tropsch synthesis begins with the simultaneous chemisorption of CO and H₂ on metal active sites. Cobalt and iron are mainly used as catalysts for this synthesis. The optimal synthesis temperature for cobalt catalysts is 170–270 °C (low-temperature Fischer–Tropsch synthesis), whereas for iron catalysts it is 250–325 °C (high-temperature Fischer–Tropsch synthesis). Cobalt catalysts typically operate at pressures of up to 130 atm, while iron catalysts operate at 20–30 atm. Improvements in natural gas conversion processes currently focus on reducing investment costs and employing larger-capacity single-train units. A characteristic feature of the Fischer–Tropsch synthesis is the sharp change in selectivity with increasing temperature. An increase in temperature may lead to catalyst self-heating and a complete loss of its ability to produce liquid and solid hydrocarbon products.

Therefore, effective heat removal is a critical requirement in the implementation of this process.

The products of the classical Fischer–Tropsch synthesis consist mainly of linear paraffinic hydrocarbons. Small amounts of isoparaffins, olefins, aliphatic alcohols, aldehydes, and acids are also formed. The relative yield of these products varies significantly and strongly depends on the catalyst and operating conditions of the synthesis. The Fischer–Tropsch synthesis products are formed according to the following principles [6]:

1. Thermodynamically, the formation of hydrocarbons of any molecular mass, structure, and type from CO and H₂ is possible, except for acetylene.
2. The probability of hydrocarbon formation decreases in the following order: methane > other alkanes > alkenes.
3. The probability of formation of normal alkanes decreases, while the probability of formation of normal alkenes increases with increasing chain length.
4. An increase in total system pressure promotes the formation of heavier products, whereas an increase in the partial pressure of hydrogen in the synthesis gas favors the formation of alkanes.

Since the synthesis of hydrocarbons from CO and H₂ is a polymerization-type process, the resulting products form a distribution of aliphatic hydrocarbons ranging from methane up to compounds containing 100 or more carbon atoms. The molecular weight distribution of these products is described by the Schulz–Flory equation [7]:

$$g_n = (1-\alpha)^2 \cdot n \cdot \alpha^{n-1}, \text{ где } g_n \text{ — mass fraction of hydrocarbons with } n \text{ number of carbon atoms.}$$

In this equation, the parameter α (Schulz–Flory alpha) represents the ratio of chain propagation to chain termination rates. The Schulz–Flory α is an important indicator of catalyst performance, as it characterizes its ability to promote the polymerization reaction. The Schulz–Flory equation imposes certain limitations on the selectivity of the most valuable Fischer–Tropsch synthesis products, namely liquid hydrocarbons: the yield of the gasoline fraction (C₅–C₁₁) and the diesel fraction (C₁₂–C₁₈) cannot exceed 48 wt.% and 30 wt.%, respectively. At the same time, solid hydrocarbon products characterized by a Schulz–Flory α value exceeding 0.9 are formed without significant limitations. This feature of the product distribution in the Fischer–Tropsch synthesis imposes a specific influence on the process design and technological configuration. In order to obtain a higher yield of liquid hydrocarbons, the synthesis is carried out in two stages (the “two-stage Fischer–Tropsch synthesis”). First, hydrocarbon mixtures rich in heavy products are produced from CO and H₂. These products are then subjected to hydrocracking to obtain middle distillates, i.e., commercial fuels such as diesel fuel and jet kerosene. At present, cobalt-based systems are considered the most promising Fischer–Tropsch synthesis catalysts, enabling the production of liquid and solid paraffinic hydrocarbons from CO and H₂ with selectivity of up to 90%. It is well

established that the activity and selectivity of cobalt Fischer–Tropsch catalysts are influenced by a wide range of factors, such as the nature of the support and promoters, the preparation method, reduction conditions, and others [8].

For the preparation of cobalt Fischer–Tropsch synthesis catalysts, impregnation is the most commonly used method. Catalysts prepared by this technique are characterized by the fact that the specific surface area of the reduced catalyst is close to that of the support, which essentially acts as a matrix controlling the formation of cobalt crystallites of a certain size. The highest yield of liquid products is achieved when the cobalt crystallite size is approximately 50–100 Å [9].

Cobalt catalysts exhibit activity in the Fischer–Tropsch synthesis only when metallic cobalt is present. Since these catalysts are typically prepared from cobalt salts, they require prior reduction at 350–500 °C (the reduction temperature depends on the catalyst composition and is an optimized process parameter).

The polymerization properties of cobalt catalysts can be significantly influenced by promoters. Oxide promoters (such as ZrO₂, TiO₂, MnO₂, and others) improve process selectivity by increasing the yield of liquid hydrocarbons [10].

Metallic promoters, typically noble metals of Group VIII, can also be used to enhance catalyst activity [11].

Their characteristic feature is ease of reduction and the ability to adsorb hydrogen in atomic form, which facilitates the reduction of cobalt species. As a result, both CO conversion and the yield of liquid hydrocarbons increase. When a metallic promoter is introduced, as in the case of oxide promoters, its concentration in the catalyst must be optimized. It should be noted that the preparation of an active catalyst for hydrocarbon synthesis from CO and H₂ imposes stringent requirements on the quality of the materials used. For example, changing the supplier of the support may lead to a noticeable decrease or even a complete loss of catalytic activity. This may be caused by changes in the phase composition of the support, the presence of catalyst poisons (such as sulfur), as well as other compounds capable of forming new phases with cobalt or promoters. GTL projects are typically aimed at supplying petrochemical products to various markets (12–18).

These markets can be divided into fuel, petrochemical, and specialty product segments. The crude oil market is the largest, most accessible, and virtually unlimited market for GTL products. Synthetic crude oil can be sold on global markets at a price approximately 30% higher than Brent crude due to the absence of sulfur, nitrogen compounds, benzene, and other harmful impurities. In the context of Russia, achieving such a price advantage is possible when synthetic crude is transported from a GTL plant to export consumers using railway tank cars or marine tankers. However, in most cases, the primary method of crude oil transportation to the market is the main pipeline system, where synthetic crude oil will inevitably be blended with conventional (“mineral”) crude oil, leading to a loss of quality differentiation. Nevertheless, the production of synthetic crude oil and its sale even at standard market prices remains economically justified in cases where the feedstock consists of low-cost associated petroleum gas, low-pressure gas, or gas from fields with reserves of less than 200 billion m³. The diesel fuel market is the most important segment for synthetic liquid fuel (SLF) end-use products. Synthetic diesel fuel surpasses petroleum-derived diesel fuel (meeting the EN590 standard) in key performance indicators: the cetane number exceeds 75 compared to 55 for conventional diesel; the content of polyaromatic hydrocarbons is 0.1% compared to 6%; sulfur content is 0 ppm compared to 50 ppm; and density is 767 kg/m³ compared to 835 kg/m³. Significant opportunities for these products exist in developed markets, where environmental issues associated with vehicular emissions represent a serious concern. In this context, cleaner GTL diesel fuel can be blended with conventional diesel fuel in order to improve the quality characteristics of the latter. A market for such “environmental additives” already exists. At present, pure GTL diesel fuel is used in specially adapted engines in Germany, Austria, and Sweden. In France, Italy, and other countries, blends of GTL and conventional diesel fuel are used. The diesel fuel market is considered the fastest-growing and most promising global petroleum product market. A projected annual growth rate of approximately 3% in diesel fuel consumption is

expected. However, even with 50% implementation of new GTL capacity projects, the contribution of synthetic diesel fuel to the total market volume would account for only about 2.3%. For this reason, the development of even very large-scale GTL capacities is not expected to cause oversupply in the market. The energy strategy of the Russian Federation envisions a future transition toward the export of high-quality diesel fuels.

The solution to this problem can be largely achieved through the development of the GTL industry at Russian gas fields. The second most important GTL product is naphtha, which is analogous to natural gas liquids (NGLs). In conventional practice, NGLs are obtained during the processing of associated petroleum gas at gas processing plants. NGLs are a highly valuable feedstock for the petrochemical industry. GTL-derived naphtha is an ideal raw material for the production of ethylene and propylene. Other GTL products, such as lubricating oils and paraffins, despite their high quality characteristics, have limited markets. Therefore, the introduction of new GTL capacities may lead to oversupply in these product segments. The synthetic liquid fuels (SLF) market is a rapidly growing sector. The main factors driving this market include the urgent need to monetize large reserves of natural gas, associated petroleum gas, and coal-bed methane that are difficult to utilize by other means such as pipeline transport or conversion into heat and electricity. This trend is reinforced by the continuously increasing global demand for liquid hydrocarbons, as well as increasingly stringent environmental regulations regarding the quality and emission characteristics of hydrocarbon fuels.

LIST OF LITERATURE

1. J.F. Freide, T. Gamlin, M. Ashley// Hydrocarbon Processing. February 2003. P. 5258
2. Braginsky, O.B., Shlikhter, E.B., Kessel, I.B., Serebrovsky, A.L. Catalysis in Industry, 2004, n. 4, p. 3.
3. Rozovsky, A.Ya. Kinetics and Catalysis, 1999, vol. 40, n. 3, p. 358.
4. Braginsky, O.B., Shlikhter, E.B. World Oil Refining: An Environmental Dimension. Moscow: Academia, 2002, p. 219. 5. J. Stell Oil and Gas, 2003, vol. 101, no. 16, p. 66.
5. G. Henrici-Olivé, S. Olivet. Chemistry of Catalytic Hydrogenation SO. Moscow: Mir, 1987.
6. R.B. Anderson, R.A. Friedel, H.H. Storch// J. Chem. Phys. 1951. V. 19. P. 313.
7. Lapidus A.L. // Izv. Academy of Sciences of the USSR. Ser. chem. 1991. P. 2681.
8. Hoang Chong Iem, Krylova A.Yu., Lapidus A.L. // Neftekhimiya, 1983. T. 23. No. 6. P. 779.
9. Lapidus A.L., Krylova A.Yu., Sadekhuddin S.M., Ghazaryan A.G., Hoang Chong Iem // Petrochemistry, 1985. T. 25. N. 4. P. 498.
10. Lapidus A.L., Krylova A.Yu., Tonkonogov B.P., D.O.Ch. Izzuka, M.P. Kapoor // HTT. 1995. N. 3. P. 90.
11. Stolyпин V. I., Shakhov A. D., Volchenko A. G., Khabibullin R. R. Improving the adsorption process of drying and purification of natural gas // Gas industry. 2007 N. 1 С 76-80
12. Patent 2147916 RFMKI 7F25J3/02 Method for separating components of natural gas /Nikolaev V.V., Gafarov I.A., Lomovskikh V.D., Molchanova Z.V. Gerasimenko M.N., Vshivtsev A.I., Stolyпин V.N. and others B.I. 2000, B I ,N. 12
13. RF Certificate No. 20785 for utility model MKI with F25J3/02 Installation for fractionation of gaseous and liquid hydrocarbon streams /Nikolaev V.V., Gafarov N.A., Lomovskikh V.D., Molchanova Z.V., Klimov V.D., Stolyпин V.I. and others B.I. 2001 N. 33
14. Russian Federation Certificate No. 26965 for Utility Model IPC 7B01D53/02 Installation for Adsorption Drying, Purification, and Low-Temperature Separation of Natural Gas / Gafarov N. A., Stolyпин V. I., Molchanova Z. V. et al. BI 2003.№ 1
15. Russian Federation Patent No. 32583 for Utility Model IPC7 с 7F25J3/00 Installation for Low-Temperature Separation of Hydrocarbon Gas / Gafarov N. A., Stolyпин V. I., Molchanova Z. V. et al. BI ,2003.№ 26
16. Russian Federation Patent No. 44801 for Utility Model IPC7 с 7F25J3/00 Installation for Low-Temperature Separation of Hydrocarbon Gas / Ivanov S. I., Mikhailenko S. A., Stol'shin V. I., et al.
17. Udut V.N, Stolyпин V N, Polotznyuk V J-V et al Russian Cryogenic com pexes for production of liquid helium and the prospects of helium industry development in Russia //JCEC 21,JCMC-06 Cryogemes. 2006,Praha.P 240.